

Reduced Order Modeling of a 1D High-temperature gas-cooled reactor simulator

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ABSTRACT

Real-time prediction of nuclear reactor transient dynamics remains computationally prohibitive with full-order multi-physics models, limiting their application in monitoring and control tasks. To overcome such limits, we present a reduced-order modeling approach that combines Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) with Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) for High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor (HTGR) dynamics. After building the POD-SINDy model from data obtained from a simplified 1-D HTGR model with varying heat transfer coefficients, we show that it successfully reduces the system dimensionality from about 14000 to 7 degrees of freedom. With a dimensionality reduction of a factor of approximately 2000, the approach still demonstrates good performance in temporal extrapolation and parameter space exploration across different values of the heat transfer coefficient, indicating that the POD-SINDy model is capable of speeding up (1-D) HTGR simulations without a significant loss in physical accuracy.

Keywords: High-temperature gas-cooled reactor, Reduced Order Modeling, Proper Orthogonal Decomposition, Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-physics modeling is essential for predicting transient nuclear reactor behavior. Classic algorithms solve the partial differential equations (PDEs) describing coupled neutronics-thermal-hydraulics dynamics, enabling, for example, full 3-D simulations of High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors across a broad range of accident scenarios [1]. However, these powerful tools, while critical for reactor design, are extremely computationally expensive, and thus fail to provide real-time predicting capabilities. Reduced order models could offer a potential solution, by maintaining acceptable accuracy while drastically reducing computational degrees of freedom.

In this work, we present a reduced-order model for nuclear reactor dynamics. We employ Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) for dimensionality reduction [2] and Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) for modeling the temporal evolution in the reduced space [3]. The resulting low-dimensional model demonstrates good performance in temporal extrapolation and parameter space interpolation. To generate training data and validate the reduced model, we implement a simplified 1-D model of a High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor, with transient dynamics induced by varying the heat transfer coefficient between graphite and coolant. The validation is performed on trajectories not included in the training dataset.

To our knowledge, the POD-SINDy methodology has not been applied to High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors, representing a novel contribution for model order reduction of coupled neutronics-thermal-hydraulics systems.

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1.1. The 1-D HTGR Full Order Model

We present here a simplified 1-D model, developed to obtain the necessary data on the coupled neutronics-thermal-hydraulics of a High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor with prismatic fuel blocks. A schematic representation of the system is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the one-dimensional prismatic HTGR considered in this work. The system is divided into two regions, the core and the graphite reflector, and it is symmetric around its left side. Coolant, graphite moderator and fuel alternate in the core as in a fuel block.

The simulator is composed of two modules coupled together, which calculate how the neutron flux and temperature distributions in the system evolve in time, and their mutual influence.

The dynamics of the neutron flux in the reactor is modeled by the 2-group neutron diffusion equations, as in

$$\frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial \phi_g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} D_g \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \phi_g + \Sigma_{t_g} \phi_g = \chi_{pg}(1 - \beta) \sum_{g'=1}^2 \nu_{g'} \Sigma_{f_{g'}} \phi_{g'} + \sum_{\substack{g'=1 \\ g' \neq g}}^2 \Sigma_{s_{g' \rightarrow g}} \phi_{g'} + \chi_{dg} \lambda C, \quad (1)$$

where the subscript g refers to the group's index, $\phi = \phi(x, t)$ is the neutron flux, D the diffusion coefficient, ν the number of neutrons released per fission, and Σ_t , Σ_f , Σ_s , respectively, the total, fission and scattering macroscopic cross-sections. The coefficients χ_{pg} and χ_{dg} represent the probability of prompt and delayed neutrons to be born in energy group g . We consider $\chi_{p1} = \chi_{d1} = 1$, and $\chi_{p2} = \chi_{d2} = 0$, hence assuming all neutrons to be born within the fast group. For simplicity, we assume a single effective precursor family, with $\beta = \sum_i \beta_i$ representing the corresponding delayed neutron fraction, and λ the decay constant.

To correctly account for the delayed neutrons feedback, the dynamics of the precursor concentration $C = C(x, t)$ is evaluated from

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \beta \sum_{g=1}^2 \nu_g \Sigma_{f_g} \phi_g - \lambda C. \quad (2)$$

The temperature distribution in the two blocks is obtained by solving the heat conduction equation,

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + Q, \quad (3)$$

where $T = T(x, t)$ is the temperature distribution, ρ the material density, c_p the specific heat capacity, and k the thermal conductivity. Q is the source term, representing the heat production from fission (no decay heat has been considered in this work). Equation 3 allows to calculate, in a simplified fashion, how the temperature distributions in the two blocks evolve, as a function of heat source and boundary conditions. The relation with the conditions in the coolant channels is obtained through

$$k \frac{dT(x_{bound}, t)}{dx} = h(T(x_{bound}, t) - T_{cc}), \quad (4)$$

where T_{cc} is the temperature in each coolant channel (kept constant, for simplicity) and h is the heat transfer coefficient between graphite and coolant. The latter is the main parameter used in this work to induce transient conditions in the system, as described in Section 3. In this simplified model, we did not include the effects of Xenon on the transient dynamics.

Both neutronics and thermal-hydraulics equations are discretized by means of the Finite Volumes method, while, to propagate the equations in time, Backward Differentiation of order 2 is adopted.

The coupling happens through the update of the neutronics constants (macroscopic cross-sections, diffusion coefficients) as a function of temperature. We use Serpent to calculate these parameters in the homogenized core region and in the reflector. Seven temperatures, ranging from 400 K to 2000 K, are used for the core, while the reflector is maintained at a constant temperature of 400 K. The evaluation of the neutronics constants at an arbitrary temperature T is then performed by logarithmic interpolation.

In Figure 2, a schematic representation of how the transient coupled simulations work is provided. First, the flux is initialised and the heat source term is evaluated. The evolution of the temperature distribution in the two fuel blocks from one time-step to the next is then calculated, assuming all thermal power to be deposited in the fuel. The average temperature in the two blocks is used to update the neutronics constants, which allow for a re-evaluation of the fast and thermal flux distributions in the system. The updated heat source term is then used as input for the thermal solver in the subsequent time step. The simulation continues until the prescribed time t_{end} is reached.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the computational scheme for the transient coupled calculations. The thermal-hydraulics solver calculates the temperature distribution in fuel and graphite in the two blocks, providing the neutronics solver with the average temperature in the homogenized core. The neutronics solver operates on the entire reactor (in the reflector, only the neutron flux is calculated), and provides the thermal solver with the necessary heat source term. \bar{T} is the average temperature of a fuel block, while q''' represents the local power density, used as an input for the thermal solver.

The calculated data are saved and used to create the reduced order model of the 1-D HTGR, as explained in Section 2. The following fields are stored: fast and thermal fluxes $\phi_1(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\phi_1}}$ and $\phi_2(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\phi_2}}$, concentration of precursors $C(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_C}$, power $P(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_P}$ and temperature of the two blocks $T(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_T}$. Each field has its own spatial domain, and thus we define a concatenated field s and a vector field \mathbf{s} , as in

$$s(t|h(t)) = [\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{s}_3, \mathbf{s}_4, \mathbf{s}_5]^T \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \mathbf{s}(t|h(t)) = (\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{s}_3, \mathbf{s}_4, \mathbf{s}_5) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_C \times N_{\phi_1} \times N_{\phi_2} \times N_T \times N_P} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_1 = C$, $\mathbf{s}_2 = \phi_1$, $\mathbf{s}_3 = \phi_2$, $\mathbf{s}_4 = T$, $\mathbf{s}_5 = P$ and all fields share the same temporal and parametric dependence. The overall dimension of s is $N = N_{\phi_1} + N_{\phi_2} + N_C + N_T + N_P$.

The only parameter considered in this work is the heat transfer coefficient h , and its variation induces the transient dynamics. Thus, we use it to generate trajectories to train and validate the ROM.

2. METHODOLOGY

We build a surrogate model of the HTGR system described in Subsection 1.1 by adhering to a two step procedure, which combines non-intrusive dimensionality reduction with ODE modeling of the reduced

dynamics. The dimensionality reduction step is controlled by two functions: an Encoder and a Decoder. The Encoder $\varphi : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^\lambda$ takes the high-dimensional vector $s(t|h(t))$ defined in Equation 5 and maps it into a low-dimensional representation $\varepsilon(t|h(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^\lambda$, with $\lambda \ll N$; conversely, the Decoder $\psi : \mathbb{R}^\lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ maps the low-dimensional vector $\varepsilon(t|h(t))$ into its corresponding high-dimensional vector $s(t|h(t))$. Given the reduced representation $\varepsilon(t|h(t))$, its dynamics is modeled according to the ODE

$$\frac{d}{dt}\varepsilon(t|h(t)) = f(\varepsilon(t|h(t)), h(t)), \quad (6)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^\lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^\lambda$ is a function that depends both on ε and $h(t)$. We define $f_A \approx f$ as a data-driven approximation of f , $\mathbf{T} = \{t_i\}_{i=1}^F$ as the set of discretized time instances where s is evaluated, $s^{1,h_1} = s(t = t_1|h(t_1))$ as the initial condition, $\tilde{s}^{i,h_i} = \tilde{s}(t = t_i|h(t_i))$ as the prediction of the surrogate model at time $t = t_i$ (the same notation applies to \mathbf{s} and $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}$) and $\varepsilon_i^{h_i} = \varepsilon(t = t_i|h(t_i))$ as the reduced representation at time t_i . In Subsection 2.1 and Subsection 2.2 we describe how φ , ψ and f_A are obtained.

The two steps are coupled in practice as follows: at time t_1 the initial condition s^{1,h_1} is mapped to its low-dimensional representation $\varepsilon_1^{h_1}$ by the Encoder φ ; subsequently, the reduced vector $\varepsilon_i^{h_i}$ at any give instant t_i is obtained by solving $\varepsilon_i^{h_i} = \varepsilon_{i-1}^{h_{i-1}} + \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} f_A(\varepsilon(t'|h(t')), h(t'))dt'$, where the integral can be solved by using standard numerical methods. Finally, the Decoder ψ is used to recover the vector field \tilde{s}^{i,h_i} from $\varepsilon_i^{h_i}$ at the time-steps of interest. In Figure 3 we provide a visualization of the described methodology.

Figure 3. Overview of the reduced order model. From the left, the initial condition s^{1,h_1} (which encompasses ϕ_1, ϕ_2, C, T and P), is mapped into the low dimensional vector $\varepsilon_1^{h_1}$. The latter is then evolved in time by solving Equation 6 (with $f_A \approx f$) through standard numerical methods, and the prediction \tilde{s}^{i,h_i} is obtained by decoding $\varepsilon_i^{h_i}$ through ψ . The color dots in the gray boxes represent the values of the reduced vector ε (4 in this example case).

2.1. Dimensionality reduction: Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

In order to construct the Encoder φ and the Decoder ψ we make use of a widely spread reduced order basis method, known as Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) [2] in the reduced order modeling community and as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in the Machine Learning one. The main idea is that we approximate the solution s of Equation 5 as:

$$s(t|h(t)) \approx \tilde{s}(t|h(t)) = \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} \alpha_i(t|h(t)) U_i, \quad \alpha_i \in \mathbb{R}, U_i \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (7)$$

where the scalar α_i is a coefficient that weights the importance of the mode U_i of dimension N , which belongs to the orthogonal basis set $\mathbf{U} = \{U_i\}_{i=1}^\lambda$. We recall that s and \tilde{s} are built as a concatenation of the fields ϕ_1, ϕ_2, C, T and P . There are two main points:

1. once \mathbf{U} has been determined, \tilde{s} is defined by only λ degrees of freedom represented by the vector $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)) = (\alpha_1(t|h(t)), \dots, \alpha_\lambda(t|h(t)))$, according to Equation 7. This means that the original high-dimensional physical system of dimension N is mapped onto a low-dimensional space of dimension λ ;
2. the solution s is projected onto a linear subspace spanned by the vectors belonging to the basis \mathbf{U} , hence the approximation is accurate with a low number of modes only if the dynamics of the original space of s evolves on a low-dimensional linear subspace.

In order to determine the optimal basis \mathbf{U} , we firstly construct the snapshot matrix $\mathcal{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times (N_t N_h)}$ from data obtained by the model of Subsection 1.1 as a collection of snapshots in time from N_h trajectories. Each trajectory starts with the same initial condition, and it is defined by the functional form of the heat transfer coefficient $h(t)$. So $\mathcal{S} = [s(t_1|h^1(t_1)) | \dots | s(t_{N_t}|h^1(t_{N_t})) | \dots | s(t_1|h^{N_h}(t_1)) | \dots | s(t_{N_t}|h^{N_h}(t_{N_t}))]$, where $h^i(t_k)$ represents the i th functional form of h evaluated at time t_k , N_t is the number of time-steps per trajectory and N_h is the number of sampled trajectories. The basis \mathbf{U} is then obtained non-intrusively by solving the minimization problem

$$\mathbf{U} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W} \in \mathcal{Y}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \|s(t_i|h^k(t_i)) - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{W}^T s(t_i|h^k(t_i))\|_2^2, \quad (8)$$

where \mathcal{Y} is the set of all λ -dimensional orthogonal bases in \mathbb{R}^N . The minimization problem of Equation 8 is easily solved thanks to the Schmidt–Eckart–Young theorem [4, 5], which states that the first λ left singular vectors of \mathcal{S} , obtained via singular value decomposition (SVD), minimize Equation 8. Hence we compute the SVD of \mathcal{S} as $\mathcal{S} = \mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{Z}^T$, where $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ and $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_t N_h) \times (N_t N_h)}$ are orthogonal matrices and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N_t N_h}$ is the rectangular diagonal matrix of singular values $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \dots \geq \sigma_{N_t N_h} \geq 0$. Hence $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times \lambda}$ is taken as the first λ columns of \mathbf{V} .

2.2. Time evolution in the reduced space: Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics

The Encoder φ and the Decoder ψ defined in Subsection 2.1 connect the high-dimensional space of the function s to the low-dimensional space of the vector ε . However, a model of the dynamics of ε according to Equation 6 is still needed: we need to find a closed mathematical form of f_A (still in a data-driven fashion). To do so, we rely on the Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) method [3], which was developed to approximate the dynamics of nonlinear systems. Following [3], we define f_A as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)) \approx f_A(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)), h(t)) = \Theta(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)), h(t)) \boldsymbol{\Xi}, \quad (9)$$

where $\Theta(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)), h(t)) = [\theta_1(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)), h(t)), \dots, \theta_p(\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t|h(t)), h(t))] \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is a library of p candidate functions $\theta_i : \mathbb{R}^\lambda \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, while $\boldsymbol{\Xi} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times \lambda}$ is a matrix of coefficients that modulates the importance of each term of Θ . The functions θ_i are chosen a priori before any computation, while the matrix $\boldsymbol{\Xi}$ is found by regression from the data. The choice of the library of functions can be driven by a priori knowledge of the system or by pure trial and error, and can be as complex as needed, although usually a polynomial form is chosen. In this work, we set a polynomial library of order 2 both for the feature and parameter libraries, as described in detail in [6].

We define $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times (N_t N_h)}$ so that H_i is the parameter corresponding to the snapshot \mathcal{S}_i . The matrix of coefficients $\boldsymbol{\Xi}$ is instead computed by regression, as follows:

1. from the snapshot matrix \mathcal{S} we construct the snapshot matrix of POD coefficients $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times (N_t N_h)} = \varphi \circ \mathcal{S} = \mathbf{U}^T \mathcal{S}$;
2. given \mathcal{A} , by using finite differences we can approximate the values of f_A per each $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_i|h(t_i))$. We call the matrix of approximated derivatives $\tilde{f}_A \in \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times (N_t N_h)}$;
3. we compute the optimal Ξ as

$$\Xi = \arg \min_{\Xi'} \sum_{i=1}^{N_t N_h} \left(\|\tilde{f}_{A,i} - \Theta(\mathcal{A}_i, \mathcal{H}_i)\Xi'_i\|_2^2 + \gamma \|\Xi'_i\|_2^2 \right), \quad (10)$$

where index i identifies the column i th of the matrices and γ is a scalar which weighs the importance of the regularization of the coefficients of Ξ .

The minimization of Equation 10 is carried out using the Sequentially Thresholded Least Squares (STLSQ) algorithm from [6]. Besides encouraging small values of Ξ through $\|\Xi'_i\|_2^2$, the STLSQ method eliminates values of Ξ at each iteration if below a given sparsity threshold: the rationale stems from the idea of promoting sparsity, which can sometimes be linked to an improvement in generalization and interpretability of f_A . We used `normalize_columns = True` as a parameter of the STLSQ algorithm in [6]. In the above process f_A only approximates the dynamics of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ found by φ without modifying it. In summary, according to the notation and vocabulary used in Section 2 and in Figure 3, the Encoder is $\varphi(s) = \mathbf{U}^T s$, the reduced vector is $\varepsilon_i^{h_i} = \boldsymbol{\alpha}(t_i|h(t_i)) = \boldsymbol{\alpha}_i^{h_i}$, the Decoder is $\psi(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and $f_A = \Theta(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, h(t))\Xi$. Notice that the dependence on the parameter $h(t)$ is implicit in s and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, and explicit in f_A .

In all experiments, we use the randomized SVD [7] as computationally faster than standard SVD when the size of \mathcal{S} is large. Prior to the SVD computation, we normalize the input fields \mathbf{s}_i according to the z-score normalization, i.e., $\mathbf{s}_i \rightarrow \frac{\mathbf{s}_i - \mu_i}{\sigma_i}$, where μ_i and σ_i are the mean and standard deviation of the field \mathbf{s}_i computed from the snapshots belonging to \mathcal{S} . We set the sparsity threshold to 0.0001 and $\gamma = 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

In this Section we test the effectiveness of the ROM described in Section 2, built from the 1D HTGR reactor data, by answering four questions:

1. **Q.1** How well can the ROM generalize to values of h not present in the snapshot matrix \mathcal{S} ?
2. **Q.2** Can a ROM constructed from trajectories with time-independent h generalize to a time-dependent $h(t)$?
3. **Q.3** How well can the ROM extrapolate in time?
4. **Q.4** What is the actual dimensionality reduction obtained?

We refer to the data used to construct the ROM via \mathcal{S} as training data, while to the data used to test the model and not belonging to \mathcal{S} as testing data. During testing, Equation 9 is solved using an implicit multi-step variable-order (1 to 5) method based on backward differentiation formula for the derivative approximation. In order to quantify the accuracy of the ROM predictions, we define the following metrics:

$$\text{nRMSE}_k(h) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{ts}} \frac{\|\mathbf{s}_k(t_i|h) - \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k(t_i|h)\|_2^2}{\|\mathbf{s}_k(t_i|h)\|_2^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{nRMSE}_{\max,k} = \max \left\{ \frac{\|\mathbf{s}_k(t_i|h(t_i)) - \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k(t_i|h(t_i))\|_2^2}{\|\mathbf{s}_k(t_i|h(t_i))\|_2^2} \right\}_{i=1}^{N_{ts}}, \quad (11)$$

where N_{ts} is the number of time steps of each trajectory of the testing data, $\text{nRMSE}(h) = [\text{nRMSE}_k(h)]_{k=1}^5$ and $\text{nRMSE}_{\max} = [\text{nRMSE}_{\max,k}]_{k=1}^5$. $\text{nRMSE}(h)$ is useful when h does not vary with time, while nRMSE_{\max} when $h = h(t)$. In Equation 11 we are using the vector notation of Equation 5, thus both $\text{nRMSE}_k(h)$ and nRMSE_{\max} are computed per field \mathbf{s}_k (where \mathbf{s}_k is defined in Equation 5). Similarly, we define $\text{nRMSE}_{\text{mean}}$ which takes the mean instead of the maximum.

Q.1: As training set we use 37 trajectories, each with time ranging from $t = 0$ s to $t = 1200$ s, with a time-step of 0.1 s. Each trajectory has a constant h over time; the training values of h are uniformly sampled from $h = 0.0$ W/(cm²K) to $h = 0.0255$ W/(cm²K). In Figure 4 we show the results obtained

Figure 4. Results on a testing set when the training set consists of multiple trajectories each with a not time-dependent h . The gray vertical line signals where the core is separated by the reflector. t_0 , t_M and t_F are respectively the initial state, the middle state and the final state.

when testing the model obtained on a test set consisting of 9 trajectories, with h (not time-dependent) sampled uniformly from $h = 0.004$ W/(cm²K) to $h = 0.027$ W/(cm²K). More specifically, in Figure 4a we show the nRMSE(h), which decreases with h and is significantly lower for the temperature field; in Figure 4b and Figure 4c we compare the prediction with the ground truth for ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 at the middle state and the final state for $h = 0.0117$ W/(cm²K).

Q.2: This paragraph extends the evaluation of the ROM's predicting capability to transients induced by time-dependent heat transfer coefficients. We remind that no direct information on the dynamics induced by a time-dependent h has been provided in the training dataset. Two different input functions are analyzed: a piecewise variation of the heat transfer coefficient and a sinusoidal functional form of it. The two functions are shown together in Figure 5a. The results obtained for the prediction of these two transients, in terms of normalized power, are presented in Figure 5b and Figure 5c. The $nRMSE_{max} = [7.6\%, 7.6\%, 7.6\%, 7.6\%, 0.4\%]$ (the indices follow Equation 5) in the transient induced by the sinusoidal $h(t)$, as defined in Equation 11. The $nRMSE_{mean,k}$ is below 2% for all the five fields.

Figure 5. Functional forms of $h(t)$ and comparison between prediction and ground truth for the normalized power during the two transients induced, respectively, by a piecewise and a sinusoidal $h(t)$.

Q.3: Figure 5 also shows the capability of the model to extrapolate over time: as mentioned, the training set is composed of transients up to a time of 1200 s, while the tests shown are performed up to 1800 s.

Q.4: In all the experiments we mapped the full space of dimension $N = 14000$ to a reduced space of dimension $\lambda = 7$, hence achieving a dimensionality reduction by a factor of about 2000.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a novel approach for model order reduction of a 1-D coupled neutronics-thermal-hydraulics system representing the essential dynamics of a High-Temperature Gas Reactor. The methodology combines Proper Orthogonal Decomposition for dimensionality reduction with Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics to evolve coordinates in the reduced space. We evaluated the reduced-order model performance by testing on transients with heat transfer coefficients outside the training set; the results confirmed satisfying capabilities of the model at interpolation in parameter space and at dimensionality reduction, with the original dimensionality successfully reduced by a factor of 2000. Additionally, we showed the model's capability of extrapolating in time. Finally, we established that the ROM is able to simulate transients with a time-dependent $h(t)$, a fundamental feature that ROMs must have in order to make real-time prediction of nuclear reactor transient dynamics.

4.1. Limitations and future improvements

Although Section 3 shows that the ROM significantly reduces dimensionality while maintaining predictive power, we signal the criticalities encountered and potential areas of improvement. Hyperparameter tuning for SINDy (sparsity threshold, form of candidate functions θ_i) requires extensive effort; in particular, minor modification of the hyperparameter set of a good working model can result in models not converging at testing time. Additionally, POD's linear projection assumption may fail for highly nonlinear, non-linearizable systems that cannot be well-approximated by few modes. This motivates a future focus on nonlinear dimensionality reduction techniques. Finally, an extension of this work will focus on an application to tridimensional HTGR.

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